

THE MESSAGES EYE CONTACT AND EYE AVOIDANCE CONVEY IN A MULTICULTURAL CLASSROOM

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ABSTRACT:

This article aims at underscoring the messages eye contact and eye avoidance send in a multicultural classroom while taking into consideration factors like culture, context, personal styles, and the co-occurrence of other nonverbal cues. The research has used the qualitative method to analyse data that have been collected from 483 participants hailing from Africa, Europe, Asia, and South America. The instruments that have been used are interviews, questionnaires, and participant observation. It has been found that eye contact and eye avoidance cross-culturally send messages like *confrontation, disrespect, discipline, authority, interest, defiance, affection, attention, confidence, credibility, honesty, engagement, seriousness, concentration, love, friendship, domination, aggression, warmth, lack of confidence, disinterest, unfriendliness, suspicion, respect, restraint, humility, inattention, dishonesty, shyness, submission, hatred, and shame*. Thus, the paper draws teachers' attention to the fact that the two nonverbal cues must be construed in interaction with factors like culture, context, personal styles, and the co-occurrence of other nonverbal cues.

KEYWORDS:

EYE CONTACT, EYE AVOIDANCE, CULTURE, NONVERBAL COMMUNICATION, MULTICULTURAL CLASSROOM.

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1. Introduction

In a world that is becoming more and more globalized, it is of signal importance to take into consideration the cultural aspects of the use of nonverbal cues, especially eye contact and eye avoidance that help convey a wealth of information, during classroom interactions. Nowadays, it is undeniable that in a myriad of countries, schools of all levels welcome students, coming from different cultural backgrounds, that may not have the same interpretations of nonverbal communication. If some nonverbal cues are given universal meanings, others have local meanings some teachers may misconstrue. For instance, eye contact, which is a mighty communication tool, is used in class to signal information people from different cultures may interpret in different ways. In addition to eye contact, eye avoidance also is a way of communicating one must seek to understand. In fact, the use of these two nonverbal cues has been dealt with by researchers, but the ways these must be understood in a multicultural classroom do not seem to be given much attention. As such, this paper aims at dealing with the types of interpretations that can be given to such nonverbal cues in a classroom composed of students that have different cultural backgrounds. The questions the paper intends to answer are: what are the messages eye contact and eye avoidance can signal in a multicultural classroom? What are the factors that should help teachers interpret such conveyed messages? Both eye

contact and eye avoidance are given different meanings depending upon cultures, personal styles, speech context, and the co-occurrence of other nonverbal cues.

It is usually helpful to heed cultural differences there are about the use of eye contact before interpreting any information it conveys during a multicultural classroom interaction. For instance, following Muhayyang et al. (2023), "In some cultures, an eye view is often interpreted as a statement of the seriousness of attention, listening, seeing, understanding, daydreaming, dreaming, confused, angry, love, sad, seductive, sensual, dominating, letting go, and indifference, all of which must be interpreted in certain socio-cultural context" (p.98). Not only have Muhayyang et al. (2023) drawn readers' attention to the fact that cultures do not have the same interpretations of eye contact, but also the crucial role context plays in the comprehension of such a nonverbal cue. The same nonverbal cue can be given different meanings depending upon context. Thus, both context and cultural differences should be valued for there to be better understanding of the very information that is signalled by nonverbal cues in a multicultural classroom. Muhayyang et al. (2023) have also postulated that "The messages communicated by the eyes vary depending on the duration, direction, and quality of the eye's behavior" (p. 98). In addition to the duration, direction, and quality of eye behavior, it should be pointed

out that the variation of the meaning of eye contact is dependent on various factors that will be dealt with in this research.

Rzayeva (2025) states that "In Western educational settings, teachers often interpret a student's lack of eye contact as inattention or disinterest. Likewise, teachers who do not look at their students may be perceived as unapproachable or disengaged" (p.273-274). According to this researcher, the way of construing eye contact in Western educational settings is different from the meaning it can have in some African and Asian cultures. In such cultures, a student's eye contact or eye avoidance may be far from expressing the idea of inattention or disinterest. Hietanen (2015) also discusses something similar. This researcher says that if maintaining eye contact is highly valued by Western Europeans, this is not the case with people that have Asian cultural backgrounds; this suggests that the information that is sent by eye contact and eye avoidance in a classroom welcoming, for instance, Asian, European, African, and American students may be comprehended in different ways. The interpretation of the two nonverbal cues can be easily wrong if a certain number of factors are not taken into consideration. It is very helpful for teachers working in multicultural classrooms to be mindful of the different interpretations eye contact and eye avoidance are given in different cultures; this is a good way to minimize misunderstanding during classroom communication in which nonverbal cues play a crucial role. About the predominance of context in the comprehension of excessive eye contact, Hietanen (2018) gives a fascinating insight according to which "one's interpretation of the meaning of another's gaze is, of course, contingent upon a number of antecedent, concurrent, and anticipated contextual factors" (p.02). Besides contextual factors, Hietanen (2018) states that "the gazer's verbal and non-verbal behavior, most importantly the verbal content and facial expressions, can have a great influence on the meaning attributed to his or her gaze" (p.02). As one can see, focusing on the sole meaning of excessive eye contact is not sufficient for its right interpretation; there are other factors that should be paid attention to for a better understanding.

Bunglowala and Bunglowala (2015) argue that teachers use eye contact to get students' attention, to encourage them, but also to control the class. They go on to state that "If a teacher looks at every student in the classroom or avoids looking at students, he conveys the attitude of intimacy, aloofness, depression or indifference" (Bunglowala and Bunglowala, 2015, p.374). Being aware of the predominance of eye contact, Ledbury and Darn (2004) advise teachers to use their eyes to express praise, encouragement, and disapproval occasionally. They also argue that eye contact that is time and effort saving is a correction technique teachers should use in their classrooms. Thus, it is a classroom management tool teachers can use to maintain discipline during teaching and learning activities.

Researchers have demonstrated what excessive eye

contact can convey as information. Following Muhayyang et al. (2023), excessive eye contact makes some students uncomfortable, awkward, and nervous. Then, they advise teachers to avoid using this cue that can become a barrier in learning. Fernandez and Caparas (2025) state a similar idea that explains that "Some students experience discomfort and distraction when exposed to direct or prolonged eye contact from teachers" (p.342). The views Muhayyang et al. (2023), and Fernandez and Caparas (2025) have shown about the drawbacks of the use of excessive eye contact should be taken into account, but it is also worth mentioning that some teachers have recourse to such a nonverbal technique for classroom management purposes. A teacher can excessively look at a student to show them that there is something wrong with their deportment; in this case, students that understand the message behind the gaze may adjust their behaviour to focus on what is being done in class. It should be pointed out that whether the use of excessive eye contact is bad or good mainly depends on the context in which it is used.

For there to be effective communication in our schools, teachers should be equipped with cross cultural nonverbal communication skills. This is essential insofar as it facilitates a better understanding of one another's emotions, intentions, attitudes, and feelings in an environment where cultures keep on conversing. Hietanen (2015) interestingly delineates that the study of eye contact is very relevant in a world where there are more interactions among people of different cultural backgrounds. Like our societies, today, our schools are places where different cultures constantly communicate through people's daily interactions. Butt et al. (2011) argue that "School is recognized as a mini society, where students of various cultures and families communicate with one another in pursuit of education" (p.41). In addition to students, what one can add is that, today, it is unquestionable that the staff of a lot of schools are composed of professionals who do not necessarily have the same use and comprehension of most nonverbal cues, especially the use of eye contact and eye avoidance that are under study in this paper. About the messages eye contact can convey, Butt et al. (2011) have indicated that teachers use this nonverbal cue to signal information such as motivation, appreciation, admiration, drawing students' attention, etc. Hans and Hans (2015) postulate that "Making eye contact with others also communicates that we are paying attention and are interested in what another person is saying. Eye contact can also be used to intimidate others" (p.48).

Hans and Hans (2015) have pointed out that eye contact has a number of communicative functions that range from regulating interaction to monitoring it, to conveying information, to establishing interpersonal connections. They explain that, in terms of regulating communication, we use eye contact to show that we are ready to speak or we want others to speak. Hans and Hans (2015) also argue that "A speaker can use his or her eye contact to determine if an audience is engaged, confused, or bored and then

adapt his or her message accordingly” (p. 48). Actually, the use of eye contact can help a person to know whether their listeners are paying attention to their speech or not; it can also be used by the speaker to gauge the level of interest and motivation of the listeners, especially when these are learners. Interest and motivation are very important ingredients for successful learning. As such, using eye contact to control and maintain these ingredients during classroom interactions can be useful.

Jongerius et al. (2020) state that “Eye contact is a fundamental aspect of nonverbal communication and therefore important for understanding human interaction” (p. 363). One can agree that eye contact is a powerful cue whose understanding is very helpful in human interactions, but what the authors have not shown is that cultures may not construe its use in the same way depending upon context and other factors. For there to be mutual understanding between people with the use of eye contact, they should seek to comprehend both the local and universal meanings of such a nonverbal cue. Thus, a competent teacher working in a multicultural classroom is a teacher that is capable of understanding what each of their students signals with eye contact and eye avoidance during classroom activities; they must also be a teacher who appropriately uses their eyes to communicate to students having different backgrounds.

Understanding eye contact and eye avoidance allows both teachers and students to get, from one another, a wealth of internal information related to attitudes, emotions, feelings, and thoughts. Teachers should usually comprehend that their own eye contact and eye avoidance are also construed by their students. They should not focus on reading learners’ nonverbal cues while overlooking their own nonverbal expressions. In class, nonverbal communication is a transactional tool by means of which the participants simultaneously send and receive information from one another. As such, eye contact and eye avoidance are used and deciphered by both teachers and learners at once. For instance, Ledbury and Darn (2004) seem to express a similar idea when they state that eyes are considered to be a powerful tool for both teachers and learners. Eye avoidance can be used to indicate the opposite of what eye contact conveys, but in order to have a better understanding, it is usually helpful to take various factors into consideration. As such, a teacher who misinterprets a student’s eye avoidance may misinterpret their eye contact as well. If cultures do not encode eye contact in the same ways, they may also have different interpretations for eye avoidance.

2. METHODOLOGY

This paper has opted for the qualitative method. In doing so, it aims at understanding the meanings teachers and students’ eye contact and eye avoidance can have in a multicultural classroom. In order to collect qualitative data, the researcher has used instruments like observation, questionnaires, and interviews. Participant observation has been used to gain a deeper understanding of how students from different levels and cultural backgrounds

use and construe eye contact and eye avoidance; the use of this type of instrument can be relevant because Jorgensen (1989) argues that it helps know the ways in which things happen. Open-ended questions have been used to collect data from students and teachers. Some interviews have also been conducted to get some teachers’ perspectives about the topic under study. These instruments have strategically been chosen to gain insights into various messages the two nonverbal cues can signal during classroom interactions.

About the participants, data have been collected from teachers and students having different cultural backgrounds; this has helped the researcher to get information about how cultures construe eye contact and eye avoidance taking into consideration other factors like context, personal styles, and the co-occurrence of other nonverbal cues. The results of this research are derived from 483 participants. There are 187 teachers and 296 students that have participated in answering the research questions. The participants hail from 22 different countries spread over four continents that are Africa, Asia, Europe, and South America. There are 168 European participants (57 teachers and 111 students), 132 African participants (60 teachers and 72 students), 103 South American participants (40 teachers and 63 students), and 80 Asian participants (30 teachers and 50 students). The age category of the teachers are between 26 and 47 years old, whereas the age category of the students, that are in high school or at university, is between 17 to 23 years old. The researcher has made a decision about obtaining data from participants of different nationalities because he wants to get insights into how people of various cultures construe eye contact and eye avoidance, especially in a multicultural classroom.

3. FINDINGS

The data are presented in regard to what has been found about the use of both eye contact and eye avoidance in different cultures. According to the data, eye contact and eye avoidance are cross-culturally used to convey messages that may be different or similar. It has been indicated that culture, context, the co-occurrence of other nonverbal cues, and personal styles importantly influence the messages eye contact and eye avoidance are used to signal. Let’s give the messages the two nonverbal cues send across the four continents whose participants have provided the research data.

The African participants have expressed that eye contact is considered to be *confrontational, disrespectful, a sign of discipline, authority, interest, defiance, affection, and attention*. As far as eye avoidance is concerned, it has been expressed that, in class, it can signal *respect, humility, submission, restraint, timidity, concentration, hatred, and shame*.

The following excerpts are derived from the collected data:

Teacher@O: *In most African cultures, people don’t see eye contact as the expression of honesty or credibility. African students can use eye contact to show their interest in what is*

being done in class as they can also avoid it in some contexts to show their respect to the teachers that have an important status in society.

Teacher@FD: *In Africa, eye contact is used by parents to discipline children when they are behaving badly. Children that understand the message that is behind may stop the behaviour without being spoken to. Sometimes, this can also be the case in class.*

Teacher@L: *Students that are very shy and respectful may avoid eye contact with their teachers. Instead of maintaining eye contact with their teachers, they may look at the wall or at the board when speaking to their teachers.*

Teacher@N: *Avoiding eye contact can be an expression of respect as it can mean disinterest. It depends on the context and on people's backgrounds. Some students that are not following can avoid any eye contact with the teacher.*

Teacher@GD: *Authorities tend to use eye contact to show their domination, whereas people that are under their control can avoid it to communicate their submission.*

Teacher@H: *In some contexts, eye contact is used by both teachers and students to show affection and interest. You can also know the meaning better if you analyse the face or the voice of the person.*

Teacher@Y: *Sometimes, when some people are angry, they may maintain eye contact with the person they are angry with to defy him. Others may avoid any eye contact to show ignorance or disinterest.*

Teacher@DC: *In most African capital cities, eye contact is becoming more and more common between people of different generations. This seems to be the case in our classrooms as well.*

Student#GF: *My parents taught me that it is disrespectful to look people of mature age in the eyes.*

Student#FT: *I use eye contact to concentrate on what teachers say.*

Student#DV: *I avoid any eye contact with a person I hate and I don't even want to smile.*

Student#GH: *When I am doing something bad and teachers look at me, when I see them, I stop because I know that they want me to stop.*

Student#UL: *We can avoid eye contact when we are humble.*

Student#TK: *When I am ashamed, I avoid eye contact with people in order not to feel more ashamed.*

Student#YM: *A good student must look at the teacher if he wants to understand the explanations.*

Student#PD: *I don't know if I am very shy, but I can't look teachers in their eyes for a while.*

Student#ZB: *When teachers explain something important I want to understand, I look at them.*

The European participants have expressed that eye contact is used to express information like *confidence, interest, credibility, honesty, engagement, seriousness, concentration, love, and friendship*. They have indicated that avoiding eye

contact can convey *dishonesty, disinterest, suspicion, a lack of confidence*, and also *shyness*. Let's show the following excerpts that are derived from both teachers and students' data.

Teacher@@AD: *People use eye contact to communicate interest and honesty. When you are interested in someone or what they say, you look at them, and if the person is honest, they also look at you.*

Teacher@@DF: *People that are confident while speaking maintain eye contact. Avoiding it in this case can mean a lack of confidence.*

Teacher@@R: *Both teachers and students must use eye contact if they want to express honesty and credibility when they speak.*

Teacher@@T: *Some people avoid eye contact because they are too shy. When you look at them, you can know from their faces that they are shy.*

Teacher@@X: *A person may avoid eye contact if they want to hide something from the person they are speaking to.*

Teacher@@C: *Maintaining eye contact is difficult for those that are not confident.*

Teacher@@TF: *If you keep eye contact, it means that you are interested, and also you are listening.*

Teacher@@S: *When students want to participate in something the teacher is talking about, they use eye contact. Their eyes then show that they want to be involved.*

Teacher@@Y: *You maintain eye contact when you are concentrated or serious.*

Student##E: *I want teachers to look at me when they speak because this makes me feel that I am loved. I want them to do that with a good face.*

Student##WA: *Eye contact helps me concentrate on what teachers say. I use it when I listen to them.*

Student##BV: *Students that don't want to learn avoid eye contact with teachers. They think of other things when teachers talk.*

Student##TR: *It is said that a liar doesn't like eye contact. I want to look people in their eyes when I speak to them.*

Student##G: *Eye contact is important because it shows your confidence and interest.*

Student##L: *We avoid eye contact when we are not interested in others.*

Student##KL: *Using eye contact means that you are sure of what you are saying.*

Student##LK: *I always keep eye contact with teachers when I want to answer a question.*

Teachers and students hailing from Asia have demonstrated that eye contact is used to convey messages such as *disrespect, confrontation, discipline, domination, defiance, attention, love, interest, and aggression*. According to these participants, people can avoid eye contact to send messages like *respect, restraint, humility, and inattention*. Here are some data that are obtained from some

participants:

Teacher@@@B: *Eye contact can mean different things, but in school context, students can use it to indicate that they are paying attention to what is being done in class. Depending on the situation, some students can maintain eye contact to defy the teacher.*

Teacher@@@JS: *In our culture, a teacher can maintain eye contact to control students that are not following in class. Thus, the students can stop the behaviour while avoiding the teacher's eyes. Some students stop automatically behaving badly when they realise that the teacher is looking at them.*

Teacher@@@YP: *Avoiding eye contact when speaking to people who have a higher status or rank is generally considered to be respectful in my culture, but depending on the context, sometimes, when eye contact is avoided where engagement is expected, the message that is sent can be inattention or disinterest.*

Teacher@@@GF: *For one reason or another, some muslim women or girls may contextually avoid eye contact with men. They may find it inappropriate, even in the classroom context.*

Teacher@@@HG: *Some very humble people may avoid eye contact when interacting with others. I know some humble and shy students that usually have problems maintaining eye contact with teachers.*

Teacher@@@KJ: *Respect can be the reason why some students avoid eye contact. Culturally, it can be inappropriate to maintain eye contact with authority figures.*

Teacher@@@PJ: *People with power usually use eye contact to show their domination, whereas those that are dominated avoid eye contact to show their respect and submission. Some students may avoid eye contact with their teachers because they see them as authorities they must always obey.*

Teacher@@@OR: *On the one hand, students that want to defy teachers may maintain eye contact with them to show that they are not afraid. On the other hand, some students can also avoid looking at teachers to show their disinterest. Before interpreting a student's eye contact or eye avoidance, it is important to have some information about their culture, but understanding the context also is helpful.*

Student@@@M: *I usually look at my teachers because I want to pay attention. I also want my teachers to look happy in class.*

Student###XD: *I look at my teachers but when they look at me, I cannot maintain eye contact with them. Even if I want to do it, I can't, I don't know why.*

Student###HN: *When the teacher explains, I look at his body or at the board in order to understand, but I don't want to keep eye contact with him. For me, what is more important is to understand the lesson.*

Student###FD: *I look at my teachers because I think that there is no problem about it. I also want teachers to look at me kindly.*

Student###HC: *When a teacher explains something on the*

board, I look at the board not at the teacher.

Student###LM: *When I speak, I don't look at anybody because if not I can't think.*

Student###PG: *I can maintain eye contact with a teacher when I am very angry with them.*

Student###AV: *There is no problem about looking at teachers. What can be a little bit difficult for some students is maintaining eye contact with their teachers. When teachers like you, they look at you with a happy face.*

As far as the South American participants are concerned, they have shown that eye contact signals messages like interest, warmth, love, engagement, honesty, confidence, and respect. Unlike eye contact, it has been demonstrated that eye avoidance expresses lack of confidence, disinterest, unfriendliness, and suspicion.

Teacher@@@AY: *I think that eye contact can mean friendship and love in my culture. People can look at each other when they are good friends or when they feel love for each other.*

Teacher@@@H: *Eye contact is generally used to show your interest; you don't look at people or things when you are not interested.*

Teacher@@@JC: *In my country in Bolivia, some people may avoid eye contact when they feel a lot of respect for people of higher rank. On the other hand, other people may think that you lack confidence and honesty if you don't look at them in the course of a conversation; everything depends on context and the kind of person you are speaking to.*

Teacher@@@LE: *If you avoid looking at a person that is speaking to you, it means that you don't respect them or perhaps you are not interested in what they are telling you. You must look at people if you want to give them your attention.*

Teacher@@@KF: *In our culture, people can avoid eye contact when they don't want to be involved in what is happening. Eye contact can be used to show that you want to take part in something.*

Teacher@@@R: *In a place like Lima (Peru), eye contact can show confidence and engagement, but this may not be the case in some remote places where people can use it to show respect.*

Teacher@@@Y: *When you are confident and being honest, you must look at the people you are speaking to, if you don't do that it is because maybe there is something wrong. What may not be good is maintaining eye contact with people for a long time.*

Teacher@@@BN: *In my culture, some people can avoid eye contact because maybe depending on the situation, they don't feel comfortable doing it. I think that it depends on people's preferences sometimes.*

Student###IC: *In class, I look at teachers when I want to understand what they explain.*

Student###IO: *When a teacher doesn't look at me in class, I feel that they do not like me or I am not good. In my*

culture, you can look at people to express your affection.

Student####UF: *When I am not following, I don't look at the teacher.*

Student####G: *When I am sure that the answer I am giving is correct, I look at the teacher.*

Student####LN: *I always look at the teacher because I want to understand everything in class.*

Student####HD: *When students are not interested in what the teacher does, they don't look at him/her; they concentrate on something else or on what their friends do.*

Student####RD: *When you are following and that a teacher looks at you, you can feel that they respect and like you as a student.*

Student####OA: *Students who don't want to learn don't look at the teacher during the explanations, they speak, they look at their friends or they check their mobile phones.*

The excerpts from the collected data show that cultures have both similarities and differences about the use of eye contact and eye avoidance. The similarities are considered to be shared across the four continents, whereas the differences are not. As such, it has been found that, depending on context, personal styles, and the co-occurrence of other nonverbal cues, the meanings the four continents have in common about the use of eye contact are *attention, interest, and love*, whereas the differences are *confrontation, disrespect, authority, defiance, confidence, credibility, seriousness, engagement, domination, and aggression*. As far as eye avoidance is concerned, participants from the four continents can interpret it as *disinterest and inattention*, but the meanings that are not shared by all of them are about *respect, humility, shyness, submission, restraint, concentration, hatred, and shame*. There are many similarities between the participants from Africa and those from Asia in terms of interpreting both eye contact and eye avoidance. For instance, across the two continents, eye contact can refer to *disrespect, confrontation, discipline, authority, defiance, attention, affection, and interest*, whereas eye avoidance is construed as *respect, restraint, humility, and inattention*. The European participants have many interpretations in common with the South American participants; they have indicated that eye contact can signal messages like *confidence, interest, honesty, engagement, concentration, and love*, whereas eye avoidance can express *dishonesty, disinterest, suspicion, and a lack of confidence*.

The data have demonstrated that not only do the meanings of both eye contact and eye avoidance depend upon cultures, but they can also be influenced by context, personal styles and the co-occurrence of other nonverbal cues as one can understand through the following answers that have been given by some participants: *"In our culture, people can avoid eye contact when they don't want to be involved in what is happening", "When teachers like you, they look at you with a happy face", "[...]I also want my teachers to look happy in class", "I know some humble and shy students that usually have problems maintaining eye*

contact with teachers", "I want teachers to look at me when they speak because this makes me feel that I am loved. I want them to do that with a good face", "In some contexts, eye contact is used by both teachers and students to show affection and interest. You can also know the meaning better if you analyse the face or the voice of the person", etc. In fact, the interpretation of eye contact and eye avoidance is influenced by various factors as it will be discussed in the following section.

4. DISCUSSION

As is suggested by the results, interpreting eye contact and eye avoidance is not a piece of cake in a multicultural classroom; there are important factors that should be heeded if one wants to comprehend the messages that are behind such cues. These factors are culture, context, personal styles, and the co-occurrence of some other nonverbal cues chiefly associated with the face if we focus on what our data have shown.

Culture must always guide teachers' interpretation of eye contact and eye avoidance. The data emanating from informants of different backgrounds have shown that cultures have both similarities and differences about the two aforementioned nonverbal expressions. Teachers must be mindful of the similarities while trying to inquire into the differences if they really want to avoid misinterpretation. For instance, according to the collected data, participants from Europe and South America can construe eye avoidance as a *lack of confidence*, whereas those with African and Asian backgrounds can understand it as an expression of *respect*. Equally, some cultures may see eye contact as *confrontational*, whereas others may consider it to be an expression of *engagement*. Authors like Muhayyang et al. (2023) have underscored the important role culture plays in people's perceptions of eye behaviour. Thus, teachers should strive to have the sheer amount of information about how cultures view eye contact and eye avoidance because, in today's globalized world, they are bound to welcome students coming from different backgrounds. A teacher that does not have a comprehensive understanding of all the possible meanings these cues have, may not succeed in contextually and appropriately conversing with their students nonverbally; such a teacher may also misinterpret the nonverbal messages they receive from their learners whose cultural perceptions may contradict. Thus, having nonverbal skills are useful for teachers in two ways; they send messages appropriately and they correctly understand what they receive from their learners.

Another important factor that influences the meaning of eye contact and eye avoidance is context as has been highlighted by some participants: *"Avoiding eye contact when speaking to people who have a higher status or rank is generally considered to be respectful in my culture, but depending on the context, sometimes, when eye contact is avoided where engagement is expected, the message that is sent can be inattention or disinterest"; "Eye contact can mean different things, but in school context, students can use it to indicate that they are paying attention to what is*

being done in class. Depending on the **situation**, some students can maintain eye contact to defy the teacher"; "African students can use eye contact to show their interest in what is being done in class as they can also avoid it in some **contexts** to show their respect to the teachers that have an important status in society"; "Avoiding eye contact can be an expression of respect as it can mean disinterest. It depends on the **context** and on people's backgrounds". In fact, the role context plays in the understanding of the use of nonverbal cues is paramount. Watzlawick et al. (1967) have underscored that a communicative phenomenon is usually incomprehensible when it is not broad enough to include the context. As such, teachers should use their cultural knowledge of the meanings of the two nonverbal cues along with the type of interpretation communication context allows. Without a good understanding and analysis of context, it is easy to misinterpret the use of eye contact and eye avoidance. Having a deep cultural understanding of the two cues while overlooking their contextual usage may lead to crossed wires. Even though the other factors also are helpful when interpreting nonverbal communication, one should bear in mind that context must be in the core; accordingly, nonverbal meaning is importantly dependent on context.

People's personal styles also can influence their use of nonverbal cues, especially the use of eye contact and eye avoidance. Personal styles do not seem to explain cultural realities, they are rather individual or family related. Some people have either their own ways of using nonverbal cues or they take such ways from their families. In multicultural classrooms, teachers should also be capable of identifying what their students' personal preferences are when it comes to using eye contact and eye avoidance; this may also help them better construe nonverbal expressions accurately. For instance, as is shown by the collected data, regardless of culture, some students' shyness makes it difficult for them to maintain eye contact with others. In addition to context and cultural differences, if teachers consider how their students personally use the targeted nonverbal cues, they can maximize their understanding while trying to avoid misinterpretation.

The co-occurrence of other nonverbal cues can change people's interpretation of eye contact and eye avoidance. For instance, when eye contact is used along with a smile or a chummy face, the information it conveys is different from that it signals when it co-occurs with a neutral or outlandish face. Some of the research participants have expressed the following ideas that emphasize that one must also take into account what can be sent by some other nonverbal cues: "I want teachers to look at me when they speak because this makes me feel that I am loved. I want them to do that with a good face"; "I also want my teachers to look happy in class"; "I also want teachers to look at me kindly"; "When teachers like you, they look at you with a happy face", etc. As one can understand through the given data, the appearance or behaviour of the face importantly influences how people comprehend the meaning of eye contact or eye avoidance. Teachers should

consider this factor if they really want to be good at deciphering what the aforementioned nonverbal cues signal during classroom interactions.

Eye avoidance can convey messages that can be construed in a multicultural classroom in different ways. Nierenberg, Calero and Grayson (2010) argue that people use eye avoidance when they are asked questions that make them guilty or uncomfortable. There may be misinterpretation if one sticks to this view without valuing the factors this paper has considered; these are cultural, contextual, personal, and other nonverbal parameters. Not only do teachers need skills to be able to relevantly interpret the various meanings eye contact is used to signal, but they should also be capable of understanding all the possible messages that are behind eye avoidance. A skillful teacher should usually consider the expression of other nonverbal cues, students' cultural backgrounds, personal styles, and context if they really want to interpret eye avoidance pertinently. Some researchers have dealt with eye avoidance, but they have not insisted on the paramount role the four aforementioned factors play for there to be relevant interpretations.

This paper has found out that eye contact is cross-culturally used to convey information like *confrontation, disrespect, discipline, authority, interest, defiance, affection, attention, confidence, interest, credibility, honesty, engagement, seriousness, concentration, love, friendship, domination, aggression, and warmth*, whereas eye avoidance, in different cultures, refers to the ideas of *lack of confidence, disinterest, unfriendliness, suspicion, respect, restraint, humility, inattention, dishonesty, shyness, submission, concentration, hatred, and shame*. These ideas about which cultures have some similarities and differences can mistakenly be deduced if all the factors that have been dealt with in this paper are overlooked when one interprets the targeted cues. Skilful teachers are those that are equipped with nonverbal competence that can allow them to communicate appropriately in a transactional way; they are both good senders and receivers during classroom interactions. Chisholm (1994) argues that effective cross-cultural communication skills help teachers create a classroom environment that encourages good interpersonal relationships. Likewise, teachers whose cross-cultural nonverbal communication is effective can easily create friendly classroom environments where interpersonal relationships have room for thrivingness.

5. CONCLUSION

This paper has used the qualitative method to inquire into the cross-cultural meanings eye contact and eye avoidance convey in a multicultural classroom taking into account four main factors that are culture, context, personal styles, and the co-occurrence of other nonverbal cues related to the face. There are 483 informants that have participated in providing the data the research analysis is based on; 187 are teachers and 296 are students, and they all hail from the continents like Africa, Europe, Asia, and South America. In the framework of data collection, the

researcher has used instruments like interviews, questionnaires, and participant observation; these instruments have been chosen to get the participants' perspectives about the meanings eye contact and eye avoidance can signal during classroom interactions. Thus, the researcher has drawn teachers' attention to the importance of considering the four aforementioned factors when sending nonverbal messages, but also when they interpret what they receive from learners.

According to the research findings, eye contact has the following meanings in cultures: in Africa, it is considered to be *confrontational, disrespectful, a sign of discipline, authority, interest, defiance, affection, and attention*; the European participants have demonstrated that it expresses *confidence, interest, credibility, honesty, engagement, seriousness, concentration, love, and friendship*; the Asia participants see it as an expression of *disrespect, confrontation, discipline, domination, defiance, attention, love, interest, and aggression*; and, in South America, it is said to mean *interest, warmth, love, engagement, honesty, confidence, and respect*. In order not to misinterpret eye contact, it has been shown that factors like culture, context, personal styles, and the co-occurrence of other nonverbal cues should usually be considered in a multicultural classroom.

So far as eye avoidance is concerned, it has been found that, in different cultures, it mainly signals the opposite of the ideas eye contact is said to communicate. As such, the Africa participants have indicated that eye avoidance means *respect, humility, submission, restraint, timidity, concentration, hatred, and shame*; according to the European informants, it sends information like *dishonesty, disinterest, suspicion, a lack of confidence, and also shyness*; the participants that are from Asia have pointed out that eye avoidance means *respect, restraint, humility, and inattention*; the South American informants see it as an expression of *disinterest, lack of confidence, unfriendliness, and suspicion*. Both similarities and differences have been found between cultures. As is the case with eye contact, teachers should always pay attention to culture, context, personal styles, and the co-occurrence of other nonverbal expressions related to the face if they want to send accurate information while avoiding misconstruing messages they receive from their learners.

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